

Trichobezoar as an Uncommon Cause of Intestinal Obstruction and Surgical Emergency: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Gastric bezoars are accumulations of indigestible material in the gastrointestinal tract that can lead to obstruction. Although rare, they are clinically significant and often associated with psychiatric and behavioral disorders, such as trichotillomania. This case report describes the clinical presentation, diagnosis, surgical management, and preventive considerations in a patient with a gastric trichobezoar and a background of psychiatric illness.

Clinical Case. A 30-year-old female with a history of moderate intellectual disability, organic schizophreniform disorder, and trichotillomania presented with progressive abdominal pain, vomiting, and marked abdominal distension. Physical examination revealed a palpable epigastric mass. Laboratory studies and abdominal computed tomography confirmed gastric chamber distension occupied by heterogeneous material. An exploratory laparotomy with gastrotomy was performed, successfully extracting a large trichobezoar.

Discussion. Gastric trichobezoars are primarily caused by chronic hair ingestion, predominantly in women with psychiatric comorbidities. Diagnosis typically requires imaging and endoscopy, but large bezoars necessitate surgical intervention. Early diagnosis and timely surgery are critical to prevent complications such as perforation and intestinal obstruction.

Conclusion. Multidisciplinary management, including psychiatric support and surgical treatment, is essential for optimal outcomes and to prevent recurrence. Education for the patient and family, coupled with continuous psychiatric follow-up, plays a vital role in comprehensive care.

KEYWORDS: Trichobezoar, Gastric obstruction, Trichotillomania, Psychiatric disorders, Surgical management, Prevention.

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INTRODUCTION

Gastric bezoars are accumulations of ingested material that can cause gastrointestinal obstruction and, although uncommon, represent a significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenge [1]. These foreign bodies can form from plant fibers (phytobezoars), hair (trichobezoars), medications (pharmacobezoars), among other materials, and usually occur in patients with a history of psychiatric or behavioral disorders, such as trichotillomania and pica [2].

Trichotillomania, a disorder characterized by a compulsive hair-pulling disorder, can lead to hair ingestion and, so, the formation of trichobezoars [3]. Although this condition is most common in adolescents and young women, it can occur in any age group and have grave consequences if not diagnosed and treated promptly [4].

Early diagnosis and multidisciplinary management are essential in the treatment of gastric bezoars. Endoscopy is the diagnostic tool of choice, allowing direct visualization and, in

Trichobezoar as an Uncommon Cause of Intestinal Obstruction and Surgical Emergency: Case Report

cases, removal of the bezoar [5]. However, in cases of large or complicated bezoars, such as the present one, surgical intervention is necessary to avoid serious complications such as gastric perforation or intestinal obstruction [6].

CLINICAL CASE

A 30-years-old female with a history of moderate intellectual disabilities, organic schizophreniform disorder, and trichotillomania, and checked by the Psychiatric Service of this unit and treated with risperidone and sertraline. She reported delayed developmental milestones in childhood, which needed a stay in a Special Education Center from ages 2 to 15. She also had two earlier cesarean sections; she denied allergies and any other significant medical history; she came to our unit with her mother due to abdominal pain. A family member reported the onset of generalized abdominal pain 1 month earlier, which she self-medicated with metamizole and hyoscine, without improvement. In the last 4 days, she began vomiting countless amounts of food, with an increase intensity of abdominal pain and intolerance to oral intake, which is why she came to our unit.

During physical examination, the patient was awake, conscious, alert, with dehydrated mucous membranes and integuments with marked pallor. She was normocephalic, had a symmetrical cylindrical neck, and no palpable adenomegaly. The chest was intact, with increased frequency of respiratory movements and use of accessory muscles. The abdomen distended, tympanic, painful to superficial and deep palpation in all four quadrants, with decreased peristalsis, and no evidence of peritoneal irritation. The lower and upper

extremities were intact and symmetrical, with preserved sensitivity, palpable distal pulses, and a delayed capillary refill of >3 seconds.

Upon admission, the patient underwent routine blood tests and imaging studies, obtaining the following data: hemoglobin 18 g/dL, hematocrit 51%, leukocytes 8,900/mm³, platelets 514,000/mm³, sodium 128 mEq/L, potassium 4.2 mEq/L, chloride 82 mEq/L, central glycemia 110 mg/dL, urea 77 mg/dL, BUN 36 mg/dL, creatinine 0.7 mg/dL, normal liver function tests, coagulation times and pancreatic enzymes. A simple abdominal computed tomography scan showed significant gastric distension with complete occupation of the gastric chamber by heterogeneous material, along with intestinal distension and air-fluid levels (Figure 1).

DIAGNOSTIC APPROACH

The diagnostic process for trichobezoars typically begins with clinical suspicion based on patient history and presenting symptoms such as abdominal pain, vomiting, and distension. Imaging techniques play a critical role:

- Ultrasound: Initial assessment tool to identify intragastric masses.
- Computed Tomography (CT): Gold standard for visualizing the bezoar's size, location, and potential complications.
- Endoscopy: Provides direct visualization and is sometimes therapeutic for smaller bezoars.

In this case, the CT scan was decisive in confirming the presence of a large gastric bezoar, necessitating surgical intervention.

Therapeutic Options and Their Relevance

The choice of therapeutic intervention depends on the bezoar's size, composition, and the presence of complications

Therapeutic Approach	Indications	Advantages	Limitations
Endoscopy	Small to moderate bezoars without complications	Minimally invasive, shorter recovery	Ineffective for large or dense bezoars, risk of incomplete removal
Laparoscopy	Large bezoars without severe complications	Less invasive than open surgery, quicker recovery	Requires advanced surgical skills, limited efficacy in extensive obstruction or perforation
Laparotomy	Large, complicated bezoars or suspected perforation	Full access for exploration and removal, effective in complex cases	More invasive, longer recovery, higher postoperative risk

SURGICAL TREATMENT

The patient underwent an exploratory laparotomy. A vertical gastrotomy of 8 centimeters was performed on the greater curvature of the stomach, exposing the trichobezoar within the gastric cavity (Figure 2). The trichobezoar was completely extracted, revealing a dense, compact, and dark mass of matted hair, typical of this pathology (Figure 3). The integrity of the gastric mucosa was verified, and the gastrotomy was closed in two layers with reinforcement via an omental patch.

After confirming hemostasis, the abdominal cavity was cleaned, and an abdominal drain was placed in the surgical bed before closing the cavity in layers. The patient was admitted to the general surgery ward where she received antibiotic therapy (IV cephalosporin), scheduled analgesia, a nasogastric tube bypass, and fasting for three days. She later tolerated a liquid diet and was gradually transitioned to a soft diet. She was discharged after six days due to clinical improvement. Outpatient evaluations revealed no complications.

Trichobezoar as an Uncommon Cause of Intestinal Obstruction and Surgical Emergency: Case Report

DISCUSSION

The presented clinical case highlights a complex medical situation involving the formation of a gastric bezoar in a patient with a psychiatric history. Bezoars are accumulations of indigestible material in the gastrointestinal tract, which can cause obstruction and other serious symptoms [7].

The patient in question has a history of moderate intellectual disabilities, organic schizophreniform disorder, and trichotillomania, which increased her risk of developing a trichobezoar. Trichotillomania is an impulse control disorder characterized by a compulsion to pull out hair, which can lead to hair ingestion and, so, trichobezoar formation [8]. Up to 20% of patients with trichotillomania may develop trichobezoars.

The clinical presentation of abdominal pain and uncontrollable vomiting is typical in cases of gastric bezoars. Abdominal distension and decreased peristalsis seen during physical examination are common findings in these cases [9]. Computed tomography is essential for diagnosis, as it allows direct visualization of the bezoar and assessment of the extent of the obstruction [10].

Endoscopy is the method of choice for diagnosis and, for treatment, allowing for direct removal of the bezoar [11]. However, in cases of large or complicated bezoars, such as the present one, surgical intervention is necessary [12]. The incidence of bezoars is low, but their impact on patients can be significant, especially in those with added risk factors [13]. The association between psychiatric disorders and bezoar formation is well documented, with studies suggesting that trichotillomania and pica are the main predisposing factors [14]. In addition, abdominal ultrasound can be helpful in finding the nature and location of the bezoar [15]. In this case, the patient underwent an urgent exploratory laparotomy, which allowed for successful removal of the trichobezoar. Studies have shown that laparotomy and laparoscopy are effective in the management of large bezoars [16].

Complications of bezoars include gastric perforation, intestinal obstruction, and hemorrhage. ¹⁰ The patient's postoperative recovery was favorable and there were no complications, underscoring the importance of prompt intervention and proper postoperative management. Patient and family education is essential to prevent recurrence, especially in patients with psychiatric disorders that predispose to bezoar formation [7]. Cognitive-behavioral therapy and other psychiatric interventions may be useful to address the underlying behaviors that lead to bezoar formation [17].

Prevention and Long-Term Management

Preventing recurrence of trichobezoars involves addressing both psychiatric and physiological aspects. Key strategies include:

- **Psychiatric Intervention:** Continuous care focusing on CBT to manage compulsive behaviors.
- **Family and Patient Education:** Recognizing early signs of recurrence.

- **Regular Monitoring:** Periodic endoscopic checks in high-risk individuals.
- **Multidisciplinary Follow-Up:** Involving surgery, psychiatry, psychology, and nutrition.

These measures are vital for sustained recovery and minimizing the need for future surgical interventions.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights the critical importance of early diagnosis and multidisciplinary management in patients presenting with gastric bezoars, particularly in those with an underlying psychiatric history. The prompt surgical intervention was decisive for achieving a favorable outcome, ensuring the complete resolution of the trichobezoar without postoperative complications.

Moreover, addressing the psychiatric comorbidities, such as trichotillomania, through continuous psychiatric care and behavioral therapy is fundamental to prevent recurrences. A comprehensive and coordinated approach, involving surgery, psychiatry, psychology, and nutrition, is essential to ensure not only physical recovery but also the long-term well-being of the patient. Education for both the patient and their family plays a pivotal role in early detection of recurrence and adherence to psychiatric treatment.

Ultimately, the integration of surgical expertise with sustained mental health support stands as the cornerstone for the effective management and prevention of trichobezoars, ensuring a holistic recovery and minimizing the risk of future episodes.

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Trichobezoar as an Uncommon Cause of Intestinal Obstruction and Surgical Emergency: Case Report

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Anexos

Figure 1. Axial section of abdominal computed tomography showing marked gastric distension with complete occupation of the gastric chamber by heterogeneous material, consistent with a trichobezoar

Figure 2. Intraoperative image showing an 8-centimeter vertical gastrotomy on the greater curvature of the stomach, exposing the trichobezoar within the gastric cavity.

Figure 3. Complete trichobezoar specimen removed from the stomach, displaying its characteristic compact, dark, and matted hair structure.